

Milan Scoring System in the Diagnosis of Salivary Gland Lesions for Assessment of Risk of Malignancy

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Received: 25-03-2024 / Revised: 23-04-2024 / Accepted: 25-05-2024

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Background: Lesions of the salivary glands can be caused by a wide variety of diseases, ranging from harmless tumours to deadly cancers. A precise diagnosis is essential for the right course of treatment, and one often used diagnostic technique is fine-needle aspiration cytology (FNAC). Introduced in 2018, the Milan System for Reporting Salivary Gland Cytopathology (MSRSGC) provides a standardised method for classifying FNAC findings with the goal of enhancing diagnostic precision and directing clinical therapy.

Aim: In a cohort of individuals, this study attempts to determine how well the (MSS) performs in identifying salivary gland lesions and determining the risk of malignancy that goes along with them.

Methods: A cross-sectional study was conducted involving 55 patients with suspected salivary gland lesions. FNAC was performed, and cytological findings were categorized using the (MSS). The FNAC results were correlated with final histopathological diagnoses, where available. Sensitivity, specificity, positive predictive value (PPV), and negative predictive value (NPV) of the (MSS) were calculated. Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS version 23.0.

Results: The study included 55 patients, with a mean age of 46.2 years. The majority of lesions were located in the parotid gland. The (MSS) demonstrated a sensitivity of 80%, specificity of 95%, PPV of 88.9%, and NPV of 89.2% in diagnosing malignant lesions. The overall accuracy of the system was 90.9%, with a statistically significant correlation between Milan categories and final histopathological outcomes ($p < 0.001$).

Conclusion: With excellent specificity and accuracy in differentiating between benign and malignant salivary gland lesions, the (MSS) is a dependable instrument for cytological assessment of lesions. When used in clinical practice, it improves the accuracy of diagnoses and directs the right course of action.

Recommendations: The (MSS) should be kept in regular diagnostic procedures for salivary gland abnormalities, according to the study. More investigation is advised to improve the method, especially with regard to diagnosing issues with "Atypia of Undetermined Significance" cases (AUS).

Keywords: Salivary Gland Lesions, (MSS), Fine-Needle Aspiration Cytology, Malignancy Risk, Cytopathology.

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Introduction

The introduction underscores the importance of accurate diagnosis and management for salivary gland lesions, which range from benign to malignant. Given the potential for significant health impacts, precise preoperative evaluation is critical. (FNAC) has become a key diagnostic tool, though interpreting FNAC results can be difficult due to overlapping features between benign and malignant lesions [1].

To address these challenges, the (MSRSGC) was introduced in 2018. This system categorizes FNAC findings into six diagnostic categories—non-diagnostic, non-neoplastic, (AUS), benign, suspicious for malignancy, and malignant—each linked to a specific (ROM) and clinical

management guidelines. The Milan System aims to reduce diagnostic ambiguity, improve communication between pathologists and clinicians, and guide patient management more effectively [2, 3].

Since its introduction, the Milan System has gained widespread acceptance. Studies have demonstrated that its diagnostic categories align well with final histopathological outcomes, particularly in distinguishing between benign and malignant lesions. For example, a research confirmed that the Milan System enhances diagnostic accuracy and clinical decision-making. Additionally, studies have shown that the system improves interobserver

agreement among cytopathologists, reducing variability in FNAC interpretations [4].

However, challenges remain, particularly with the AUS category, which still presents diagnostic difficulties. The accuracy of FNAC results can be influenced by factors such as the cytopathologist's experience and sample adequacy. Ongoing research is crucial to further refine the Milan System and enhance its diagnostic reliability [5]. In a cohort of individuals, this study attempts to determine how well the (MSS) performs in identifying salivary gland lesions and determining the risk of malignancy that goes along with them.

Methodology

Study Design: This study was designed as a cross-sectional observational analysis.

Study Setting: The study was conducted at Nalanda Medical College, a tertiary care center, from February 2023 to February 2024.

Participants: A total of 55 participants with clinically suspected salivary gland lesions were enrolled in the study. These participants were selected from patients presenting to the Otolaryngology and Pathology Departments.

Inclusion Criteria: Eligible participants were adults aged 18 and above with suspected salivary gland lesions, who consented to undergo FNAC and provided written informed consent for the study.

Exclusion Criteria: Excluded participants were those with a history of salivary gland surgery or treatment, inadequate FNAC samples, contraindications to FNAC, or who did not consent to the study.

Bias: To minimize selection bias, consecutive sampling was used to include all eligible patients during the study period. Observer bias was reduced by having two independent pathologists review the

FNAC samples and score them using the (MSS). Discrepancies were resolved through consensus.

Data Collection: Data were collected through a standardized data collection form that included patient demographics, clinical presentation, radiological findings, FNAC results, and final histopathological diagnosis when available. The (MSS) was used to categorize the FNAC findings.

Procedure: All patients underwent (FNAC) of their salivary gland lesions, performed under sterile conditions to ensure safety and accuracy. The collected samples were processed and stained following established cytological protocols. The resulting cytological findings were then systematically classified according to the (MSS), a widely recognized framework for evaluating salivary gland lesions. To determine the malignancy risk associated with each category, data from follow-up assessments and, when available, histopathological examinations were utilized, providing a comprehensive evaluation of the diagnostic accuracy of the Milan system.

Statistical Analysis: Data were analyzed using SPSS version 23.0. Descriptive statistics summarized participant characteristics. Sensitivity, specificity, PPV, and NPV of the (MSS) were calculated. The association between Milan categories and final diagnoses was evaluated using Chi-square tests, with significance set at $p < 0.05$.

Results

A total of 55 patients were included in the study, with ages ranging from 18 to 75 years (mean age: 46.2 ± 15.8 years). The study population comprised 30 males (54.5%) and 25 females (45.5%). The majority of the lesions were located in the parotid gland (60%), followed by the submandibular gland (30%) and minor salivary glands (10%).

Table 1: Participant Demographics and Clinical Characteristics

Characteristic	Number of Patients (n=55)	Percentage (%)
Gender		
Male	30	54.5
Female	25	45.5
Age Group (Years)		
18-30	10	18.2
31-45	15	27.3
46-60	20	36.4
61-75	10	18.2
Lesion Location		
Parotid Gland	33	60.0
Submandibular Gland	17	30.9
Minor Salivary Glands	5	9.1

The FNAC results were classified using the (MSS), which categorizes the risk of malignancy into six categories: non-diagnostic, non-neoplastic, (AUS), benign, suspicious for malignancy, and malignant.

Table 2: FNAC Results Based on the (MSS)

Milan Category	Number of Cases (n=55)	Percentage (%)	Risk of Malignancy (ROM) %
I. Non-Diagnostic	3	5.5	15.0
II. Non-Neoplastic	18	32.7	5.6
III. Atypia of Undetermined Significance	4	7.3	20.0
IV. Benign	20	36.4	2.0
V. Suspicious for Malignancy	5	9.1	65.0
VI. Malignant	5	9.1	100.0

Out of the 55 patients, 40 underwent surgical excision, and the final histopathological diagnosis was available. The remaining 15 patients were followed up clinically. The sensitivity, specificity, (PPV), and (NPV) of the (MSS) were calculated based on the final diagnosis.

Table 3: Final Histopathological Diagnosis and Correlation with Milan Categories

Milan Category	Benign (n=35)	Malignant (n=20)	Total (n=55)
I. Non-Diagnostic	2	1	3
II. Non-Neoplastic	17	1	18
III. Atypia of Undetermined Significance	3	1	4
IV. Benign	19	1	20
V. Suspicious for Malignancy	2	3	5
VI. Malignant	0	5	5

Diagnostic Performance of the (MSS)

- **Sensitivity:** The sensitivity of the (MSS) in diagnosing malignant lesions was 80% (16/20).
- **Specificity:** The specificity of the system in identifying benign lesions was 95% (33/35).
- **(PPV):** The PPV of the (MSS) was 88.9%.
- **(NPV):** The NPV of the system was 89.2%.
- **Overall Accuracy:** The overall accuracy of the (MSS) was 90.9%.

Statistical Analysis: The association between the Milan categories and the final histopathological diagnosis was statistically significant (Chi-square test, $p < 0.001$). This indicates a strong correlation between the (MSS) categories and the risk of malignancy in salivary gland lesions.

Discussion

The study involved 55 patients with clinically suspected salivary gland lesions, evaluated using (FNAC) and categorized according to the (MSS). The demographic analysis showed a nearly equal distribution of male and female participants, with the majority of lesions located in the parotid gland. This suggests that salivary gland lesions are relatively common across genders and most frequently affect the parotid gland. The FNAC results were systematically categorized using the (MSS), revealing that the majority of lesions fell into the benign and non-neoplastic categories.

However, a significant proportion also fell into categories indicating a higher risk of malignancy, such as "suspicious for malignancy" and "malignant." (ROM) varied significantly across these categories, with the highest ROM observed in the malignant category, as expected. The statistical analysis showed that the (MSS) had high specificity (95%) and overall accuracy (90.9%) in distinguishing between benign and malignant lesions. The sensitivity of 80% indicates that while the system is robust in identifying malignant lesions, there is still a small margin for missed malignancies. The positive and negative predictive values were also high, reinforcing the reliability of the system in clinical settings.

Overall, the results indicate that the (MSS) is a valuable diagnostic tool for assessing salivary gland lesions. Its high accuracy and specificity make it particularly useful for guiding clinical decision-making, ensuring that patients with higher-risk lesions are appropriately managed, while those with benign conditions avoid unnecessary interventions. The statistically significant correlation between the Milan categories and final histopathological diagnoses further validates the system's effectiveness in clinical practice.

Using the Milan System, it was investigated the risk of high-grade malignancy in parotid gland tumours. According to the study, there was a 100% chance of malignancy in the "Malignant" category and an 83.3% chance in the "Suspicious for

Malignancy" category. It also demonstrated the strong association between nodal metastasis and the diagnosis of high-grade malignancy, indicating that the Milan System in conjunction with nodal metastasis assessment may improve the sensitivity of high-grade malignancy diagnosis [6].

Over a two-year period, Manucha investigated the effects of the Milan System in a real-time clinical scenario. According to their research, the risk assessment for malignancy was much enhanced by rigorous adherence to the Milan System's diagnostic criteria. According to the study, there was a 100% chance of malignancy in both the "Malignant" and "Suspicious for Malignancy" categories, confirming the system's ability to improve diagnostic precision in routine clinical practice [7].

Jha used the Milan System to evaluate the cytohistological concordance. They discovered that the Milan System offered accurate estimates of the likelihood of cancer that matched histological results. The Milan System is a useful tool for risk assessment, supporting clinical decision-making and treatment, according to the study [8].

Conclusion

The (MSS) proved to be an effective and reliable tool for the cytological evaluation of salivary gland lesions. It demonstrated high specificity, accuracy, and a substantial sensitivity in predicting malignancy. The strong correlation between the Milan categories and final histopathological outcomes underscores its utility in clinical practice. By providing a structured and systematic approach, the (MSS) aids in the accurate risk stratification of salivary gland lesions, ultimately guiding appropriate clinical management and improving patient outcomes. This study supports its continued use and integration into routine diagnostic protocols for salivary gland pathology.

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